

AIJACLA

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs

Vol. 1

January, 2021

About the Journal

An International,
Double-blind,
Peer-reviewed and
Annually published
Journal.

Contact Details

Email:

aequitasvictoria@gmail.com

Helpline Number:

8473808112

Office Address:

H/o Shri Sarthak Aryan,
C/o Shri Subodh Kumar,
Old Madhya Bihar Gramin
Bank Building,
Sakurabad
P.O.: Sakurabad,
Dist: Jehanabad,
PIN: 804425 (Bihar).

Published By

**Aequitas Victoria
Foundation**

www.aequivic.in

AEQUITAS VICTORIA FOUNDATION PRESENTS ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL AFFAIRS

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

Broadly the Journal welcomes research works from each branch of law like: Human Rights, Humanitarian Rights, IPR, Environmental Law, Public and Private International Law, Air and Space Law, Drone Law, Martial Law, Sports Law, Fashion Law, etc. It even encourages contributions from panel discussion or conference reports based on the topics of recent developments in the field of law. Further, case commentaries, law book reviews, legislative and policy analysis are also welcomed. The journal will also publish contributions that are not expressly from the discipline of law but establishes a relation with any of the legal matters and gives it an interdisciplinary character.

However, comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws.

SCOPE

The scope of this journal extends to the entire world transcending all national boundaries of the States. It is an international journal aimed at establishing a global network of research and analysis in the field of law. The medium of publication will be primarily **American English** subject to the majority opinion of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, and the Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee.

The Journal is expected to be a globally open accessed journal subject to the technical limitations and international or regional laws in force or existence anywhere either internationally or nationally.

The journal intends to cover all fields of law including-

1. International Conventions passed by International or Global Bodies;
2. Regional Conventions, Rules, Policies, etc. passed by Regional Organizations that are recognized globally;
3. Rules, Policies, By-laws, etc. passed by any Inter-state bodies provided such matters influence the relationship between two or more countries that are recognized as sovereign under the international rules;
4. Any other Conventions, Laws, Rules, etc. that are not directly recognized by any international or global bodies or agencies but are going to influence or has an impact on the diplomatic relationships between two or more countries;
5. Cases decided by International Adjudicating Authorities;
6. Any Laws, By-laws, Enactments, Policies, etc. passed by a proper legislative authority, competent courts, authorities with proper legal recognitions in any sovereign country;
7. Conference, Seminar, Colloquium, etc. reports that are based on topics of law;
8. Lectures from eminent professionals in the field of law, or lectures on legal topics from eminent personalities;
9. Researches made on Theories relevant to the field of Law;
10. Any researchable topic from any discipline provided the subject-matter of such research shall properly establish the nexus with the legal institutions, instruments, or any other subject-matter of law; and
11. Results of researches carried out independently either as an individual, group, or as an organization in the field of law.

However, the journal shall not publish any material related to the following either in whole or in part subject to the approval of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee-

1. Comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws;
2. Political opinions even if based on legal topics that are suspected of influencing voting behavior of the citizens of any sovereign country against the provisions of an established legislations either international, regional, or local, or is expected to incite rebellion or conflict against any popularly established government; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee;
3. Any discriminatory opinions regarding racial, gender, or any other class of people, or comments in favor of any particular group, institution, organization, party, community, etc.; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee; or
4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

BOARD OF EDITORS

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. (Dr) Chintamani Rout

HOD. Department of Law
North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong

Senior Editor

Prof. (Dr) Yugal Kishore

Professor of Law, ICFAI Law School,
ICFAI University Dehradun, Former
Professor, Registrar, Vice-Chancellor
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Senior Editor

Dr. Heru Susetyo

Assistant professor, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Chairman of the Center for Islam and
Islamic Law, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Senior Editor

Mrs. Ronaldah Lerato Karabo Ozah

Director- Litigation, Research and
Advocacy and Lecturer, Centre for
Child Law, University of Pretoria, South
Africa.

Senior Editor

Dr Dhruvajyoti Das

Associate Professor, Department of
English, Cotton University

Senior Editor

Dr. Sachin Ghimire

Medical Anthropologist and Filmmaker
Assistant professor, Department of
Public health, Manamohan Memorial
Institute of Health Sciences(MMIHS),
Kathmandu, Nepal.

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Dr. Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor, University Law
College Gauhati University

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Dharmashastra
National Law University, Jodhpur

Associate Editors

Ms. Moushita Dutta

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Mrs. Mageswary Siva Subramaniam

Lecturer with Faculty of Law,
Multimedia University (Malacca
Campus), Malacca, Malaysia.
Visiting lecturer, Lingnan University,
Hong Kong

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Family Law,
Dharmashastra National Law University
(DNLU), Jabalpur.

Mrs. Rima Borthakur

Former Senior Manager, Document
Review department in Thomson Reuters
(Pangea3), New York City.

Associate Editors

Mr. Prithvi Raaj Choudhury

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Associate Editors

Mr. Amey Pandey

Co-Founder CLAT Junction, Working
with Safe in India Foundation

EXPERT COMMITTEE

**Prof (Dr) Bhaskar Kumar
Chakravarty**

Visiting Professor of Law Royal Global
University, Former Professor Dean and
Head Department of Law, Gauhati
University, Founder Head of
Department of Law, Tezpur University

Dr Gautami Dutta

Principal R.K.B. Law College

Dr Anup Kumar Ray

Principal, Goalpara Law College

Prof (Dr) Atul Chandra Talukdar

Dean School of Social Science &
Humanities, University of Science &
Technology Meghalaya

Dr Ajay Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Dr Md. Sultan Haidar Alam

Principal NERIM Law College

Dr Kasturi Gakul

Assistant Professor of Law
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Dr Bimal Kumar Baishya

Associate Professor (Rtd.), University
Law College Gauhati University

Dr Sujata Bhattacharyya

Principal Nowgong Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Editor Nyaijyoti, All Assam Lawyers
Association

REVIEW COMMITTEE

Mrs. Dimpy Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashmi Gogoi

Research Scholar Gauhati University
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Mrs. Karishma Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Darshana Deepak Das

MA in English Litt (Specialization in
Indian Literature), PGT in Potential and
Concept Academy, Working as an SME
in AMF Edu Solutions
Designation: Member Content

Suyash Pranay Tripathi

PGDCPLP, National Law School of
India University Bangalore, LLM
National Law University, Odisha
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Anya Behera

LLM from National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB from
KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashi Gupta

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB
Vivekananda Institute of Professional
Studies, New Delhi
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Alekh

LLM, National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Srishti

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Aadya Ambastha
Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Ishan Mishra

Student
ICFAI Law College, Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Assessment Committee

Girisha Sinha

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Prachi Prem

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Monalisa Choudhury

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Ishan Mishra
Student at ICFAI University Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Pranay Rathore

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Riya Kumari

Student at University Law College,
Hazaribagh
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Shreya Gupta

Student at JIMS Engineering
Management Technical Campus, Noida
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Prachi Nayan

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB, ICFAI
Law School, Dehradun
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Saloni Sharma

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Bomkesh Mandal

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Riya Sharma
Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Basuri Poddar

Student at National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

CORE TEAM (MANAGING COMMITTEE)

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary

Ms Vidisha Dixit

Hon'ble Member

Mrs Pranati Boruah

Hon'ble President

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Hon'ble Member (Founder)

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Hon'ble Member

Mr Sarthak Aryan

Hon'ble Member (Co-Founder)

ADMINISTRATIVE SECTION

Executive Committee

Chief Executive Officer

Ms Kashmiri Khanam

Assistant Professor, Dhubri Law
College, Research Scholar, Central
University of Haryana

Executive Officer

Ms Saloni Sharma

Fairfield Institute of Management and
Technology, New Delhi
Executive Officer

Ms Darshee Madhukallya

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Content Designer

Ms Abhishree Kashay

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Basnuri Poddar

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Gautami Chakravarty

KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar

Executive Officer

Ms Riya Kumari

University Law College, Hazaribagh

Content designer

Bonaini Deori

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Ms Nijhum Roy

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Puja Bardhan

West Guwahati Commerce College

Event Manager

Ms Nargis Choudhury

Former Lecturer, School of Law and
Judicial Sciences, Apex Professional
University, Arunachal Pradesh

Executive Officer

Mr Chetan Anand Mahapatra

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Shreya Gupta

JIS Engineering Management Technical
Campus, Noida

Content Designer

Ms Dikshita Nanda Nath

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Mr Arunabh Chakravarty

Department of English, Gauhati
University

Event Manager

Mr Debanjan Das

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Disciplinary Committee

Chairman

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Rtd. Police Officer, Assam Police
Hon'ble Member Managing Committee,
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Former Assistant Professor NERIM
Law College, Advocate Gauhati High
Court and Research Scholar North-
Eastern Hill University, Hon'ble
Member The Managing Committee
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

**Advocate Rajendra Singh
Suryavanshi**

Advocate, Supreme Court of India

Grievance Redressal Committee

Chairman

Dr Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor
University Law College Gauhati
University

Dr Ajoy Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Member, All Assam Lawyers
Association

Mrs Roseleen Deori

Assistant Professor
Nowgaong Law College

VOLUME 1
(Editorial Special Issue)
2020

AJACLA

Ms Vidisha Dixit
Hon'ble Member The Managing
Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Media Cell

Mrs Kangkana Goswami
Assistant Editor NE News

Mr Sandeep Deo
Founder, India Speaks Daily
Mrs Prity Deka
Assistant Manager, Axis Bank

Mr Bishaldeep Kakoti
Founder, The Youths Mind

IT Section

Ishita Gupta

United College of Engineering and
Research, Prayagraj

Mr Sarthak Aryan

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam, Hon'ble Member The
Managing Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sl No.	Title of Papers and Names and Designations of Authors	Page No.
SECTION A: RESEARCH PAPERS		
1	Affirmative Principle: Making, Breaking and Shaking (MBS) Approach of Judiciary <i>-Dr Rangswami D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, Karnataka</i>	1 - 17
2	Clinical and Continuing Legal Education- Interface for Confidence Building Between Law Students and Legal Professionals in Contemporary India <i>- Dr. Md. Sultan Haidar Alam, Principal, NERIM Law College</i>	18 - 29
3	A Critical Appraisal of the Legal Service Authorities Act with Special Reference to Lok Adalat <i>- Dr. Dhiraj Bhusan Sarmah, Former Faculty of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University & Dr. Plabita Saikia, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	30 - 49
4	Establishment of DNA Data Bank in India: A Legal Analysis <i>- Dr. Ranjit Sil, Assistant Professor, Department Of Law, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong</i>	50 - 64
5	Ecocentric Approaches of the Restorative Justice Theory Vis-à-vis the Legal Issues of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Baghjan Blowout Case in Assam <i>- Dr. Matiur Rahman, Assistant Professor of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University</i>	65 - 76
6	A Comparative Study on Secondary Patenting on Pharmaceutical: Striking A Balance Between Competition Law and IPR <i>- Dr. Kakumani Katakya, Faculty of Law Gauhati University</i>	77 - 90
7	Community and Environmental Protection- - In Search of the Lost Spring of Happiness of the North-Eastern Region <i>- Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, Principal, Nowgong Law College</i>	91 - 106
8	National Emergency: A Comparative Analysis of Emergency Laws in India USA and Germany <i>- Abhishek Kumar Khaund, Advocate. Gauhati High Court</i>	107 - 124
9	Legal Frameworks Relating to Use of Pesticides on Horticultural Activities Vis-à-vis Climate Change <i>- Bonani Deori, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Mritunjoy Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	125 -145
20	The Arms Act, 1959: A Legal Analysis and Comparative Study with USA <i>- Bikash Sen Deka, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	146 -168
11	Comparative Study on Intergovernmental Tax Immunities under the Federal Constitutions of Australia, Canada, India and USA <i>- Bandita Das, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	169 - 177
12	Unlawful Activities and Prevention Act: Balancing National Security with Citizen's Rights <i>- Girisha Sinha, Research Assistant under Advocate Ritesh Kumar Patna High Court</i>	178 - 191
13	An Analysis of the Legal Framework of the Co-operative Banks in India	192 - 215

	- Bidikha Gogoi, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
14	Parole- The Reformative Instrument of Punishment in Prisonization - Nayana Medhi, Former Faculty of Law, Indraprastha University	216 -228
15	Assam Police and Its Organizational Structure - Dr. Anup Kr. Ray, Principal, Goalpara Law College	229 - 271
SECTION B: ARTICLES		
16	Anti-Defection Law: A Conflict Between the Right to Dissent and the Integrity of the Political Party - Apurva Mehta, B.A. LL.B. (Criminal Law Hons.), 5th Year, National University of Study and Research in Law, Ranchi	273 - 281
17	Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore - Paras Gupta, B.A.LL.B.(Hons.), Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University	282 - 287
18	Lack of Uniform Code of Conduct to Address the Judges in India - Saloni Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology & Riya Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology	288 - 294
19	Rejuvenating the Right to Equality and Life under the Paradigm of Transformative Constitution - Dr. Daisy Changmai, Faculty of Law, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam, Former Principal of Dibrugarh Hanumanbux Surojmal Kanoi Law College	295 - 301
20	Genital Mutilation- An Appeal for Legislative Response in India to Outlaw the Menace - Dr. Karavi Barman, Assistant Professor, N.E.F Law College, Guwahati	302 - 311
21	Surrogacy in India: A Legal Perspective - Dr. Shrutimala Goswami, Assistant Professor, NERIM Law College & Arunav Barua,, Research Scholar, Assam Don Bosco University	312 - 319
22	Merger and Amalgamation of Companies in India: AN Analysis of Its Impact on Various Stakeholders - Purbaja Sarmah, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	320 - 330
23	Human Rights Crisis amongst IDPs in Assam: Issues and Challenges - Dr. Gautami Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh	331 - 337
24	Protective Discrimination under the Constitution of India - Pallabi Nath, LL.M 1 st Semester, Tezpur University	338 -345
25	Mob Lynching as a New Offence Emerging in India: A Study with a Special Reference to Assam - Nargis Choudhury, Former Faculty of Legal Studies, School of Law and Juridical Sciences Apex Professional University, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh	346 - 355
26	The Doctrine of Pious Obligation and Its Relevance under the Hindu Law in the Present Time -Titikhya Barkataki, LL.M, 1st Semester, Gauhati University	356 - 363
27	COVID-19 Pandemic: Justice Demands for Increasing Deterrence in India	364 - 370

- Jayanta Boruah, Research Scholar, North-Eastern Hill University, Former Assistant Professor of Law & Advocate & Sarthak Aryan, BALLB (3rd Year) National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam

SECTION C: LEGAL ESSAYS

- 28 **Traditional Ecological Knowledge and Biological Diversity Act, 2002: A Critical Analysis** 371 - 378
- Dr. Ravi Kanta Mishra, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, North-Eastern Hill University
- 29 **Trial by Media: A Hindrance in the Path of Justice and Fairness** 379 - 384
- Bidisha Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Kaustabh Moni Sarma, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 30 **Payment of Rent in Commercial Lease Contracts in Context of the COVID Crisis** 385 -391
- Clarissa D'Lima, Student Kirit P. Mehta School of Law, NMIMS Deemed-to-be University, Mumbai
- 31 **Adultery was Never a Crime: It is a Moral Wrong** 392 - 397
- Aadarsh Kumar Shrivastava, B.A.LL.B. 10th semester, Government New Law College Indore MP
- 32 **The Legal Protection for Consumers in Conducting E-Commerce Activities in India** 398 - 403
- Dikshita Nanda, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 33 **"Rarest of Rare Case"- Capital Punishment** 404 - 408
- Devika Warriar, Bharata Mata School of Legal Studies, Kerala
- 34 **Mob Lynching in India: A Threat to Mankind** 409 -413
- Nabanita Baruah, Student (BALLB 7th Sem), Department of Law, NERIM Law College
- 35 **Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India** 414 - 418
- Farzin Naz, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 36 **Impact of Lockdown on Migrant Workers whether a Humanitarian or Human Rights Crisis?** 419 - 426
- Nikhil Moitra, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam
- 37 **Right to Privacy and Data Protection Law in India with a Brief Comparative Analysis with UK and USA** 427 - 433
- Bandana Saikia, Student, Symbiosis Law School Pune
- 38 **Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak** 434 - 440
- Bulbul Kumari, Student, Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur
- 39 **Arrest of Tax Evaders under the Central Goods and Service Tax Act 2017** 441 - 446
- Hunseng Tungkhang, Student, NERIM Law College

SECTION D: CASE COMMENTARY

- 40 **M/S. Nandhini Deluxe v. M/S. Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd** 447 - 454
- Natesh Kumar, B.COM; LL.B.(HONS.), School of Law, SASTRA Deemed University
- 41 **The Interpretation of the Law of Limitation by the Indian Supreme Court during the COVID-19 Pandemic** 455 - 457
- Dr. Smarita Mohanty, Member, State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Odisha
- 42 **Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma** 458 - 460

	- <i>Namrata Chakrabarty, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	
43	Dunlop Pneumatic Tyre Co. Ltd. V. Selfridge & Co. Ltd.	461 - 463
	- <i>Chetna Priyam, BA LLB (Hons.), ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	
44	Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India	464 - 467
	- <i>Sristi Ray, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Kanika Chugh, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
45	Ashok Kumar Kalra v. Surendra Agnihotori (SLP No. 23599 of 2018)	468 - 470
	- <i>Monalisa Choudhury, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
46	Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors.	471 - 475
	- <i>Rajat Gupta, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Vaishnavi Pandey, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
SECTION E: LEGISLATIVE ANALYSIS		
47	Relevance of Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPs) Act, 1985	476 - 480
	- <i>Shivangi Pandey, LL.B.(CONST. LAW SPZ.) (5th Year), University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun</i>	
48	Analysis of the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill, 2020	481 - 485
	- <i>Masia Baruah, Student BALLB 6th Semester, NERIM Law College</i>	
SECTION F: BOOK REVIEW		
49	Just Mercy: A Story of Justice and Redemption	486 - 487
	- <i>Aniket Jadhav, Student, Government Law College, Mumbai</i>	
50	Book Review on Judiciary, Judges and Administration of Justice	488 - 489
	- <i>Ishan Mishra, Student, ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	

SECTION (B) ARTICLE

CONTEMPT OF COURT: AN URGENT REQUISITE TO RE-EXPLORE

Section:	B
Category:	Article
Paper Code:	RA-PG-04
Page Number:	282 - 287
Date of Publication:	February 10, 2021
Citation:	Paras Gupta, Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore, 1, AIJACLA, 282, 282-287, (2021).

DETAILS OF AUTHOR(S)

Paras Gupta,

B.A.LL.B.(Hons.)

Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University

Email id: guptparas2000@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The laws on contempt of court, the most controversial issue, has once again been put in the dock, over their incompetency to elucidate the wafer-thin distinction of contempt of court with the right to speech and expression and the magnanimity of them that have given people the courage and a chance to lower the prestige of judges and courts and to undermine the integrity and devotion of judges and the judicial system of India. The sanctity of the distinction between Freedom of Speech and Contempt of Court lies in the unabated occurrences of Contempt of Court in India. This paper deals with the pressing need of making the laws stringent on the contempt of court and the necessity of setting a model before all, to hamper the events of bringing down the poise and authority of the courts.

KEYWORDS

Contempt, Freedom of Speech, Judiciary, and Supreme Court

INTRODUCTION

Contempt of Court, the most controversial issue, has once again come into the limelight, this time, by the tweets of Prashant Bhushan. Time and again, the voices have been raised to elucidate and ratify the wafer-thin difference between Right to Speech and

Expression and Contempt of Court. Contempt of Court is defined under Contempt of Courts Act, 1971, seems unclear, as there occur unabated instances of contempt in India wherein the thin line between free speech and contempt of court has been constantly jumped and disrespected.

Contempt of Court alludes to the offense of irreverence or insubordination towards a courtroom and its officials that contradicts or challenges the equity, authority, and poise of the court. Contempt of Court, as a protected force, is vested with the Supreme Court, giving the Apex Court, power under Article 129 of the Constitution of India to punish the offenders for the contempt of itself¹. Article 129 of the Indian Constitution states that “*The Supreme Court of India shall be a court of record and will have all the forces of such a court including the ability to rebuff for contempt of itself*”². The High Court too, under Article 215 of the Indian Constitution has been empowered to punish the people for contempt of itself³. While a fundamental thought of a contempt law is to rebuff the individuals, who don't regard the sets of the courts, in the Indian Law, hatred is likewise used to rebuff those whose discourse brings down the nobility of the court and meddles with the organization of equity.

UNABATED INSTANCES OF CONTEMPT OF COURT IN INDIA

The instances of contempt of courts in India continue unabated. It is not for the first time that a person like Prashant Bhushan was tried before the Apex Court for disrespect of the Court or its officers. The

¹ Contempt of Court: Time for a relook?, Clear IAS, (Oct. 2020, 05, 09:00 AM), <https://www.clearias.com/contempt-of-court/>.

² Constitution of India 1950, Art. 129.

³ Constitution of India 1950, Aart. 215.

antiquity of these instances can be long traced. Moreover, it is also not the first time for Prashant Bhushan to commit this offense. In 2009 also he had made allegations of corruption on former Chief Justices while giving an interview to Tehelka Magazine, whose proceedings are still pending before the Apex Court⁴.

There have been several high-profile cases of contempt in India in the last two decades. For instance, M.V.Jayarajan, a politician from Kerala's Communist Party of India, was imprisoned for four weeks by the Apex Court for using the Malayalam term, ‘human’(idiot) in a speech criticizing the judiciary⁵. Another instance, when a politician was punished for contempt of court can be found is in the case of EMS Namboodiripad, when in a speech criticizing the judiciary, he asserted that the Communist theorists like Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels had considered the judiciary to be an “*instrument of oppression*”⁶.

Moreover, in 2002, a popular writer and activist Arundhati Roy was held guilty for contempt of court

⁴ Bhandra Sinha, SC refuses to accept Prashant Bhushan's explanation in 2009 contempt case, The Print, (Oct. 2020, 10, 01:14 PM), <https://theprint.in/judiciary/sc-refuses-to-accept-prashant-bhushans-explanation-in-2009-contempt-case/478540/>.

⁵ Prashant Reddy & Kian Ganz, A guide to contempt law, Mint, (Oct. 2020, 11, 02:00 PM), <https://www.livemint.com/Politics/vwdCg7zPRgLANLWwNvPl eO/A-guide-to-contempt-law.html>.

⁶ Should the courts be above scrutiny: Debate rekindles with politician jailed for calling judge an idiot, The News Minute <https://www.thenewsminute.com/article/should-courts-be-above-scrutiny-debate-rekindles-politician-jailed-calling-judge-idiot-23082>.

after she avowed that the judiciary was “*smothering contradiction*”, in an article titled ‘The Great Common Good’⁷.

The legal system in India too is not able to sojourn the disseminating instances of contempt of court in India. Despite the judgments being pronounced time and again by the Apex Court concerning the contempt of court, they are hardly able to make an impact on the continuance of instances of lowering the prestige of judges and courts. Still, the government of India has turned a deaf ear to the vital need of amending the Contempt of Courts Act, 1971.

ANTIQUITY BEHIND RECKONING CONTEMPT OF COURT UNDER ARTICLE 19 OF INDIAN CONSTITUTION

From the very beginning, when the talks on adding contempt of court as a curtailment to the freedom of speech and expression were hot in the constituent assembly, the views bifurcated. While some members were against the amendment proposed by T.T. Krishnamachari for adding contempt of court in restrictions under Article 19, some sustained the amendment.

The views were two folded. R.K. Sidhva, a member of the Constituent Assembly, criticized the assumption that the judges will use the law cautiously with a view that “*Judges have not got two horns; they also are liable to commit mistakes. For what reason would it be a good idea for us to show such a great amount of tolerance to them? The interest of the public must be safeguarded*”. Biswanath Das has even gone to the extent, terming the very move to table the amendment as ‘*tyranny of the drafting committee*’.

Positioning the amendment as filling a lacuna rather than expanding the scope of Article 19, T.T. Krishnamachari was of the view that “*as contempt of court law was already in existence, as was the case with defamation and public order provisions, it had to be expressly protected from being overwritten by the final Article 13*”. Moreover, Ambedkar’s response to the whole debate rested on legal technicalities. He was of the view that if contempt of court is not added as a reasonable restriction, the contempt laws would have to be abrogated as they would conflict with the fundamental rights chapter.

Finally, after a bit of wrangling and the exchange of views, the amendment was adopted by the constituent assembly with the subject of contempt of

⁷ A. G. NOORANI, A case for a new approach to contempt of court, *The Hindu*, (Oct. 2020, 11, 10:30 AM), <https://frontline.thehindu.com/cover-story/a-case-for-a-new-approach/article32422986.ece>.

court being added in restrictions under Article 19(2) of the Indian Constitution⁸.

AN ARCHAIC CONTEMPT OF COURTS ACT, 1971

The proceedings initiated by the Supreme Court for criminal contempt of court against the lawyer-activist Prashant Bhushan in the context of the comment made by him on social media targeting the current Chief Justice of India Sharad Arvind Bobde has once again brought under focus the need for reviewing the law on Contempt of Court. The Contempt of Courts Act, 1971 lays out the system corresponding to investigation and punishment for contempt.

The contempt laws of India are old and need to be reanalyzed. The cumulative instances of contempt of court evince the inefficacy of the laws in India to hamper the intrepidity of the offenders. Section 12 of the Contempt of Courts Act, 1971 deals with the retribution for the contempt of court. Under Section 12 of the Contempt of Courts Act, 1971, a contempt of court can be rebuffed with a straightforward detention which may stretch out to a half year or with a fine which may reach out to 2,000 rupees or both. Also, a denounced might be released or the discipline granted might be transmitted on a

⁸Sruthisagar Yamunan, Concerns about contempt laws came up in the constituent assembly- and were never fully addressed, (Oct. 2020, 27 09:00 AM), <https://scroll.in/article/968596/concerns-about-contempt-laws-came-up-in-the-constituent-assembly-and-were-never-fully-addressed>.

statement of regret being made by the blamed to the fulfillment for the court⁹.

The problem here lies with the stringency of the laws for punishing the offenders. Just by giving an apology, a person will be free from the transgression that he has committed by putting a question mark on the legal system of India. Moreover, the punishment given for undermining the dignity and respect of the judicial system is also not too stern. The recent case of Prashant Bhushan is a vivid example of this fact. Despite setting an example for the future, the provisions under the Contempt of Courts Act, 1971, gird the hands of the judiciary to impose a fine of just Rs. 1 on a person like Prashant Bhushan. Maybe, the amount imposed as a fine was to worry a millionaire like Mr. Bhushan in finding a coin of Rs.1¹⁰, but it gives a negative expression of the mind of people. This was not the first time that such a minimal amount was decided as a fine for the offense of contempt of court. EVS Namboodiripad, the then chief minister of Kerala, was only penalized with a fine of Rs. 50 for undermining the dignity of the judiciary. Moreover, the renowned person like Arundhati Roy was left by just giving a warning and

⁹ Contempt of Courts Act, 1971, Punishment for contempt of court, (Oct. 2020, 28, 09:45 PM), https://www.indiacode.nic.in/showdata?actid=AC_CEN_3_3_0005_197170_1517807319029§ionId=21665§ionno=12&orderno=12.

¹⁰ M.P. Joseph, Time to revisit contempt laws (Oct. 2020, 29 03:17 PM), <https://www.theweek.in/news/india/2020/09/14/opinion-time-to-revisit-contempt-laws.html>.

not initiating any proceedings against her for the contempt of court¹¹, clearly evincing that the magnanimity of the laws in India gives people the courage and a chance to lower the prestige of judges and courts and to undermine the integrity and devotion of judges and the judicial system of India.

CONTEMPT OF COURT IN A FACE-OFF WITH RIGHT TO SPEECH AND EXPRESSION

The aspect of the fundamental right to speech and the contempt of court doesn't seem to be novel. It is hard to mark the thin line difference between both. Often, the politicians, academicians, and scholars have expressed their anguish over the fundamental right to speech being diluted by including contempt of court as a reasonable restriction. Article 19(1) (a)¹² of the Constitution of India talks of the freedom of speech and expression. In a democracy like India, freedom of speech and expression is indispensable. Freedom of speech and expression means the right to express one's own opinions and convictions through any communicable medium or visible representation freely such as gestures, signs¹³, and by words of mouth, printing, writing, pictures, or any other mode.

¹¹ Contempt case against Rahul: He is not alone, CPM doyen EMS Namboodiripad was once fined Rs. 50 for contempt, Times Now, (Oct. 2020, 30, 04:45 PM), <https://www.timesnownews.com/india/article/sc-accepts-gandhis-apology-a-look-at-other-high-profile-criminal-contempt-cases/515249>.

¹² Constitution of India 1950, Art. 19(1).

¹³ Lowell v. Griffin, (1939) 303 US 444.

The expression connotes also publication and the freedom of the press is included in this category.

For a very long time, there has been a tussle and struggle on the removal of contempt of court from the restrictions given under Article 19(2) of the Indian Constitution. The reasons given for the same are long and unceasing. A democratic state requires transparency at all levels. When the judiciary is questioned, it should be able to defend itself with the facts to instigate rational thinking and not get offended and manifest contempt to silence criticism. Moreover, there have been several judgments favoring these voices. In *Amard v. Att Gen of Trinidad and Tobago*¹⁴, Lord Atkin observed that “*whether the power and position of an individual adjudicator or due supervision of justice is concerned, no wrong is committed by any individual from the public who practices the normal right of reprimanding, in compliance with common decency, in private or public, the public demonstration done in the seat of equity. Egalitarianism is not a sequestered issue. She must be allowed to endure the respect and scrutiny, even though outspoken, the remarks of the general population.*” Moreover, in *Brahma Prakash Sharma and Ors v. State of Uttar Pradesh*¹⁵, it was held that “*the character of an adjudicator is inside the constraints of reasonable and sensible analysis*

¹⁴ *Amard v. Att Gen of Trinidad and Tobago* (1936) A.C. 322 (P.C).

¹⁵ *Brahma Prakash Sharma and Ors v. State of Uttar Pradesh*, AIR 1954 SC 10.

regardless of whether it is simple slander or criticism of the appointed authority”.

The views in approbation of contempt of court being continued as restriction are no less. In *Sunday Times v. the U.K.*¹⁶, it was held that *“The activity of these changes, since it passes on with its commitments and obligations, might be dependent upon such conventions, limitations, conditions or punishments as are suggested by the law and are elemental in a just society for keeping up the position and fair-mindedness of the legal executive”*. In *Aswini Kumar Ghose v. Arabinda Bose*¹⁷, the Court observed that *“if an impression is made in the psyche of the public that the adjudicators in the most noteworthy court in the land follow up on incidental contemplations in choosing a case, the certainty of the general population in the organization of equity will undoubtedly be subverted and no greater devilmment than that can be envisioned”*. In *D.C. Saxena v. Hon’ble the Chief Justice of India*¹⁸, it was further observed that *“any criticism about the judges or the judicial system which disintegrates the faith in the objective approach of the judges or which hampers the administration of justice and brings the administration of justice to ridicule must be forestalled”*.

Contempt of court is an injury to the public as it, in general, make a misgiving in the psyche of the individuals concerning the reasonableness and capacity of the appointed authority or deters actual and prospective litigants from placing a complete reliance upon the court's administration of justice, and is likely to cause embarrassment in the mind of the judge himself in the discharge of his legal obligations¹⁹. The intensity of disdain of the court is important to keep up the grandness and poise of the adjudicators and to vindicate their authority²⁰. The time has come to revisit the contempt laws in India. The cumulative instances of contempt of courts mark it as a right time to accept willingly and enthusiastically that there is a pressing need to bring some decent, stringent, and tough changes in the laws to solve the issue of unhampered instances of contempt of courts. The necessity of a clear set of guidelines, of what is acceptable or not can't be ignored. In the end, the regressive and languishing debates are futile unless imperative and adequate steps are taken to elucidate the distinction and to resolve the deep-rooted conflict between the right to free speech and contempt of court.

CONCLUSION

¹⁶ *Sunday Times v. U.K.*, (1979)2 E.H.R.R. 245.

¹⁷ *Aswini Kumar Ghose v. Arabinda Bose*, AIR 1953 SC 75.

¹⁸ *D.C. Saxena v. Hon’ble the Chief Justice of India*, 1996 SCC (7) 216.

¹⁹ *Brahma Prakash Sharma v. State of U.P.* 1953 SCR 1169.

²⁰ Markandey Katju, It's time to amend law on contempt of court, *The Times of India*, (Nov. 2020, 01, 09:00 AM), <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/satyam-bruyat/its-time-to-amend-law-on-contempt-of-court/>.